

Fake News in Times of Conflict: AI-Driven Disinformation during the Israel-Iran Crisis

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Abstract

Fake news has become a significant threat in the current landscape of geopolitical tensions. After the wars in Ukraine and the Gaza Strip, the new conflict between Israel and Iran has brought to the forefront the increased risk of information warfare alongside conventional warfare. In this new conflict, artificial intelligence tools have been used on a large scale to generate fake news, photos, and videos. In this context, the article investigates the role of artificial intelligence in generating and disseminating disinformation during the crisis between Israel and Iran. By analysing AI-generated content, the study highlights how new technologies amplify the speed, scale, and apparent credibility of false narratives. The paper explores relevant case studies and recurring patterns of AI-generated disinformation. The conclusions emphasize the need for effective mechanisms to detect false information and international regulatory frameworks to combat AI-facilitated information manipulation in conflict zones. This paper may be of interest to researchers, journalists, policymakers, and cybersecurity specialists who are concerned about the impact of emerging technologies on the information environment.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence; disinformation; fake news; information warfare; Israel–Iran conflict; media manipulation; deepfake*

Introduction

In the digital age, wars are no longer fought exclusively on conventional battlefields, but also in the information space, particularly on social networks, where disinformation has become a strategic weapon (Shao et al., 2018; Stella, Ferrara, & De Domenico, 2018). With the emergence and rapid development of artificial intelligence-based technologies, the ability to create and spread false but convincing content has increased significantly (Shoaib et al., 2023; Danry et al., 2024; Sahebi & Formosa, 2025). These tools are widely used in major geopolitical conflicts, including the current crisis between Israel and Iran, where AI facilitates the generation and dissemination of false narratives that can influence public opinion and destabilise the regional environment (EDMO, 2025).

In the case of the crisis between Israel and Iran, there has been an unprecedented proliferation of automatically generated content, including deepfake images and chatbot-generated texts, which are then widely distributed via bots on social media (Murphy, Robinson, & Sardarizadeh, 2025). These tools not only facilitate the rapid creation of false narratives but also their viral amplification, reaching millions of users in real-time (Stella, Ferrara, & De Domenico, 2018).

Moreover, the cumulative effect of AI-facilitated disinformation is not limited to distorting facts but also affects public trust in legitimate sources of information, which complicates the intervention and response of authorities and traditional media (Danry et al., 2024).

This dynamic necessitates a multidisciplinary approach to effectively understand and counteract the phenomenon. In addition to theoretical studies on the cognitive and social mechanisms that favour the spread of disinformation (Shoaib et al., 2023), it is essential to analyse specific case studies, such as the disinformation campaign in the Israel-Iran conflict, in order to identify emerging patterns and propose tailored solutions.

The current literature provides a solid basis for understanding the impact of AI on disinformation in modern conflicts, but also highlights the need for more in-depth research focused on the particularities of each conflict and the development of effective response mechanisms. This article complements this direction with an applied

analysis of the Israel-Iran crisis, making a relevant contribution to the field of artificial intelligence-assisted information warfare.

Materials and methods

This research adopts a qualitative content analysis approach to investigate the role of artificial intelligence in generating and disseminating disinformation during the Israel–Iran conflict (2024–2025). The methodological design aims to identify the typologies and mechanisms through which generative AI technologies have been used to manipulate information and influence public perception. The content analysis was complemented by a review of secondary sources, including academic studies, NGO reports, and journalistic investigations.

Technological evolution: from automation to generative artificial intelligence

Recent transformations in the field of artificial intelligence have led to a fundamental shift in the way disinformation is created and disseminated (Vlăduțescu & Stănescu, 2025; Voinea, 2025). While early forms of online content automation relied on simple redistribution algorithms or networks of bots that replicated information, the emergence of generative artificial intelligence has completely redefined information strategies.

This new technological stage enables the autonomous creation of texts, images, sounds, and videos with a high level of realism, making it difficult to distinguish them from authentic content. Large Language Models (LLMs), such as GPT, Claude, or Gemini, have transformed automatic text generation into a fast, coherent, and contextualised process. They can produce seemingly credible news, official statements, or analyses tailored to the audience, journalistic style, and regional language, thereby amplifying the psychological and social impact of disinformation.

At the same time, text-to-image and text-to-video tools (Kaur et al., 2024) have facilitated the rapid production of deepfake material capable of simulating war scenes, official statements, or non-existent atrocities. Recent studies have shown that these AI-generated visual representations have a high credibility rate due to their aesthetic realism and the absence of obvious indicators of falsification.

This technological evolution can be summarised by three fundamental dimensions that explain the amplification of the disinformation phenomenon:

- (1) speed – the instantaneous production and distribution of false content exceeds the ability of media institutions to react;
- (2) scalability – the possibility of simultaneously generating thousands of variants of the same message, culturally and linguistically adapted for different audiences;
- (3) credibility – the visual realism and narrative coherence of the generated products lend increased verisimilitude to false content, blurring the line between reality and fiction.

Therefore, the transition from automation to generative artificial intelligence has amplified the volume of false information available online, as well as its ability to influence the perceptions, emotions, and political decisions of the public. Disinformation has become a systemic problem in the global digital environment, and AI now acts as a multiplier of false narratives, shaping public discourse and affecting informational stability on an international scale. In the context of the Israel–Iran conflict, such materials have been used to induce panic, manipulate international public opinion, and compromise legitimate media sources.

Artificial intelligence and disinformation in the contemporary geopolitical context

The conflict between Israel and Iran, which broke out in the second half of 2024 and continued throughout 2025 (Raine et al., 2024), was not only a military confrontation but also an intense information competition in the digital environment. This crisis marks a significant stage in the evolution of global information warfare, being considered the first major confrontation in which generative artificial intelligence tools were widely used to produce and disseminate disinformation.

The geographical focus of the phenomenon extends beyond the borders of the leading actors—Israel and Iran—to include regional and global spheres of influence. Automatically generated false narratives spread rapidly on social media in the Middle East, Europe, and the United States, influencing public perceptions and international diplomatic reactions. This expansion highlights the global nature of AI-assisted disinformation and its relevance to global information security.

The Israel–Iran conflict is a logical continuation of recent information crises, such as those generated by the war in Ukraine (Stănescu, 2022; García-Marín & Salvat-Martinrey, 2023) and the confrontations in the Gaza Strip (Stănescu, 2023). These precedents provide important insights into understanding patterns of narrative and visual manipulation, as well as analysing how artificial intelligence amplifies the speed, scale, and plausibility of false content during periods of geopolitical tension.

Thus, although disinformation is not a new phenomenon (Stănescu, 2023), it has undergone radical transformation with the rapid evolution of digital technologies, particularly artificial intelligence. Previous studies have highlighted the role of social networks in amplifying low-credibility content, contributing to the polarisation of public opinion and the deterioration of democratic dialogue (Shao et al., 2017; Stella, Ferrara & De Domenico, 2018). Currently, however, the emergence of generative artificial intelligence marks a paradigm shift, with the unprecedented expansion and sophistication of information manipulation mechanisms.

Tools such as deepfake creation systems and automatic text generation models have significantly increased the complexity and impact of disinformation. These technologies facilitate the fabrication of false content and induce a heightened perception of authenticity, providing persuasive explanations that reinforce trust in false narratives (Shoab et al., 2023; Danry et al., 2024). In times of conflict, this dynamic heightens the risks to societies, as access to accurate information becomes crucial for informed public and political decision-making.

International publications have thoroughly documented how AI has been used to spread disinformation in the Israel–Iran conflict. Case studies highlight the role of deepfakes and automated messages in generating confusion and destabilising international perceptions, while reports from non-governmental organisations emphasise the "liar's dividend" effect—the widespread loss of trust in authentic information as a result of the proliferation of false content.

At the same time, the literature focuses not only on diagnosing the phenomenon, but also on identifying solutions. Several international organisations propose a comprehensive countermeasure framework based on the development of advanced detection technologies, large-scale media education, and the creation of international regulations tailored to the specific needs of generative AI. Empirical research confirms the effectiveness of critical education and public awareness in reducing vulnerability to information manipulation (Danry et al., 2024).

Results

An analysis of media content produced during the conflict between Israel and Iran (2024–2025) reveals a concerning trend: the widespread use of generative artificial intelligence to produce and disseminate misinformation. Materials published in the international press emphasise that the war between the two states became one of the first conflicts in which generative tools were systematically used for propaganda and information manipulation purposes.

Numerous articles have documented the emergence of fake images and videos, created using text-to-image and text-to-video technologies, depicting scenes of attacks or non-existent official statements. These materials, produced within minutes of the actual events, circulated widely on social media platforms, accumulating millions of views before news outlets or fact-checking organizations could react. Thus, the speed at which false content is generated and distributed far exceeds the capacity of traditional verification mechanisms, amplifying the effect of disinformation (Table 1).

Table.1 Example of AI-generated / manipulated content

No.	Example of AI-generated / manipulated content	Details
1.	Official Iranian and Israeli media channels broadcast misleading or AI-generated images related to the conflict.	Several images did not match the actual locations or time of events and were later verified as false.
2.	One widely circulated social media post purported to show a jet damaged after being shot down in the Iranian desert.	However, a closer examination revealed clear signs of AI-generated manipulation: civilians around the aircraft appeared to be the same size as nearby vehicles, and the surrounding sand showed no evidence of impact.
3.	AI deepfake videos and footage from video games were circulated online as real combat scenes from the Israel–Iran war.	The report highlights 'video game footage passed off as real combat' and AI-generated clips distorting perceptions of the conflict.
4.	Viral video allegedly showing an explosion at Tehran's Evin Prison suspected to have been generated by AI.	Fact-checkers identified visual artefacts and inconsistencies, suggesting AI-generated content and a lack of independent verification.
5.	An image circulated on social media, claiming to show an Israeli retaliatory strike on Iran, but was later confirmed as old or unrelated.	The fact-check concluded that the images were taken from earlier, unrelated events.

A central element observed in these materials is the scalability of false messages. Artificial intelligence systems have enabled the simultaneous production of thousands of variants of the duplicate content, culturally, linguistically, and emotionally tailored to different audiences. In this way, the same narrative has been reconfigured for diverse audiences—from regional audiences in the Middle East to Western audiences—ensuring the global spread of manipulated perceptions.

Numerous cases of deepfakes were also identified, distributed even by official channels or seemingly credible accounts, which presented images of alleged attacks, victims, or political leaders. Subsequent analyses showed that many of these images were generated using specialised software, and some video sequences came from old archives or other conflicts, being recontextualised to support propaganda narratives. This high visual credibility of AI-generated content contributed to blurring the line between reality and fiction, exploiting the public's trust in video material as indisputable evidence.

At the same time, media institutions and digital platforms faced significant challenges in identifying and limiting the dissemination of these materials. Even though there are moderation policies and tools for detecting synthetic content, the technological evolution of generative artificial intelligence constantly exceeds the response capabilities of these mechanisms. Many platforms reacted late, removing or labelling the materials only after they had already gone viral.

Overall, the analysed content outlines three key directions in the transformation of disinformation through artificial intelligence: the speed with which false materials can be produced and distributed, the scalability of messages that allow them to be adapted to different audiences, and the visual and narrative credibility that gives them the appearance of authenticity. These dimensions reveal that the transition from automation to generative AI has significantly transformed the contemporary information landscape, rendering disinformation a systemic issue with direct implications for global public perceptions, social stability, and political decision-making processes.

Conclusions

The analysis of media content and case studies from the Israel–Iran conflict (2024–2025) reveals that generative artificial intelligence has become a central tool in the contemporary information warfare architecture. Unlike traditional forms of manipulation, which require time, human resources, and technical expertise, new models of automatic text, image, and video generation enable the instant creation of credible narratives that are difficult to distinguish from reality.

The research results show that speed, scalability, and visual credibility are the main factors that amplify the impact of AI-generated disinformation. Fake content can be generated in seconds, replicated in thousands of culturally or linguistically adapted versions, and distributed globally before media institutions or authorities can react. In this context, false information becomes a strategic vector of influence, capable of affecting public perceptions, eroding trust in traditional media, and shaping international political and diplomatic responses.

Documented cases show that both official media channels and networks of automated accounts have contributed to the amplification of disinformation, exploiting emotional tensions and the lack of real-time information verification. This convergence between technology and propaganda transforms the digital space into an information battlefield, where truth becomes relative and perception becomes the primary weapon.

At the same time, the analysis underscores the necessity for international regulatory mechanisms, tools for the automatic detection of AI-generated content, and media literacy education for users. The combination of technological skills and critical thinking is becoming essential to protecting the global information ecosystem.

In conclusion, the Israel–Iran conflict represents both a military confrontation and a turning point in how technology is redefining truth, trust, and communication in the digital age. While past wars were fought with conventional weapons, future wars will be determined by control over information and the ability of artificial intelligence to construct—or distort—perceived reality.

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